

The keynesian multiplier and its effect on productivity

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Abstract

Productivity is importantly seen as a factor of small value against the changes of demand and the Keynesian multiplier, what this article is showing is the controversy between interest rates and productivity using many assumptions that our vocation is not to prove but to analyse deeply using logic and intuition, what we defend in our sophism is the fact policymakers could come in rescue to companies that have the political duty and the nationalistic obligation to uprise their productivity using expenditures of states and that could still defend our sophism as an econometrics and social discourse that uses some intuitive assumptions allowed for a critical word.

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1 Introduction

Productivity has been a steady subject for scholars to apprehend and use appropriately, the Keynesian multiplier has effectively some urgent effect on productivity changes during a period of time, what we are discussing in this article is how state capital could come out for helping companies to get along with their accountings: short rates are another aspect of our sophism, it is importantly understood that whenever a change in short rates had come productivity is getting better off, short rates are willing to increase the economical cost of borrowing money from the IMF if billions of pounds are nicely exchanged with gold and its standard before the green currency can be a whale that

smoothly if used rationally would likely to allow productivity to avoid inflation shortcomings which is a drag on companies labour force: what i do state is that both interest rate and the keynesian multiplier have all the power to explain the changes occurring somehow under the productivity during a harsh recession or a *boom*.

2 The keynsian equilibrium between demand and supply with respect to the Gold

$$Y(i, T, t) = Z(i, T, t) + G_0 \tag{1}$$

Where i is risk free rate and T is the tax rate and t is time.

Y is the supply function, Z is demand and G_0 is public spending when sir keynes has insisted on the role of the state into coming on rescue to the whole state of equilibrium. What is important in the above equation is the very reminder that that supply in an economy has not an effect on the liquidity pension very importantly arguing about when the interest rate i can be adjusted toward spelling over the whole equation toward what keynsians can place above their wallets, the real stupid crucial thing in the macroside of public spendings is their unwillingness about productivity, the state is not yet approved for being productive while addressing its power into reviving the whole economy, the keynsian multiplier is what classicals have neglected once they were about to explain the laissez-faire anytime they have been steady in encouraging regulations and money droppings anytime the state of any great equilibrium that acknowledges what classicals are in the essence: if there comes that demand rises by a bit due to consumption of households the productivity of companies is less assumed to change upward if the keynsian multiplier is sticking to a certain upcoming result, empirically it means that the level of productivity is augmented if consumption is about to rise a little bit due to households, $p = \alpha m + \epsilon_t$, the level of productivity is explained partly by the propensity to consume, people willingness to rise their needs is not opposed to companies vouloir to ameliorate their labour forces. ($\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$) Productivity has other aspects which wishfully explain the movements of productivity downward, if demand decreases because of a hike in short rates or because of a windfall tax this might discourage productivity which means that investments for instance are not able to discourage productivity in a low productive environment: what this means is the following:

$$p_t = I_t + K(t)$$

Where I_t are investments and $K(t)$ is the capital policymakers are willing to use adequately to uprise productivity in the long run, what John has explained is the Keynesian importance of the state in regulating the economy and rise productivity forecasting the

role of subsidies and exportation costs quietly speaking.

$$K(t) = \beta \frac{di}{dt} + dm(t) + \epsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ What this equilibrium means is the portion of income that is used by banks due to a change in short rate and a change in consumption on the capital companies use to update productivity, it's much more about Keynes multiplier seen as an important factor of renewing the professional sphere that rely on this capital K about to be used wisely.

$$K(t) = i(t) + \sum_{i=t}^T m_i$$

Where m_i is the keynesian multiplier at time i

The level of interest rate and savings is willing to force companies to assure a capital that rises over a pilling up or accumulation of consumption functions in a great period of time, the letter John Keynes had adressed to reagon before the elections has importantly said that bailouts are not quite useful, they are willing to improve productivity in the short run while any drop in currency or arguably interest rate has a role firstof all in adequating companies when they are reluctant because of money, the cultural moral is not a waste in productivity, it's rather that interest rate even with an upward projection can permit productivity to increase without saying the opposite if growth in a whole or demand is helped by the government.

The Gold standard is seen very crucial when the stock market is down, gold as a rescue commodity is losing importance in a desert when thirst is the need, this paradox is willing to advocate a rule for gold, when gold quantity rises inflation doesn't harm people a lot during a recessionary gap, above the expectations of the return gold has been offering could be this equilibrium very crucial to the reader

$$g = i + R + I + \epsilon$$

where i is the interest rate, R is the stock return and I is the return on investments.

$\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$

What is important in the GOLD STANDARD is the self inducement it is taking as far as the multiplier would be in the essence: if productivity is seen as a factor of growth then this equilibrium should hold permanently using the fact we have linked the capital states use to save companies productivity during a recession to interest rate changes in the above equation.

3 KEYNES AND PRODUCTIVITY SMOOTH CHARACTER

$$p_t = \alpha Z(i, T, t) + \epsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where Z is demand, p is productivity and ϵ is a normal variable.

If demand is willing to rise this arguably makes productivity better if the beliefs of companies takes into consideration the real welfare of customers, in a low productivity environment investments are discouraged and the role of the Keynesian multiplier is to rise consumption using expenditures in a form of a capital addressed to not worsen companies productivity in the short run: What the above equilibrium is showing is demand explaining productivity in an econometrics relation, the normal variable is hiding all the other aspects that affect productivity, such the level of technology for instance, the slope of the function can be positive when to allow demand to explain why in a low productive environment there is a trade off between demand adequacy in rising productivity and its power for time consistency and difference between lagged demands function and productivity, arguably we can say:

$$p_t = \beta \int_0^t Z_t dt + m_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where m is the Keynesian multiplier.

Demand in general is accumulated between a reference time zero and a stopping time t when productivity is the linear regression affected by past demands in the same level during a recession everytime we could add up a portion of consumption to the sum of interpolated demands.

$$dp_t = di(t)dt + \epsilon_t$$

Where $i(t)$ is the short rate prevailing at time t .

When short rates tend to rise I have already argued against this fact: PRODUCTIVITY DEPENDS ON RATE CHANGES, it's rather change in productivity what depends on rate changes, and this is stemming out from my assumption my very first equation about wealth and capital making, the capital $K(t)$ is willing to explain how it is ruled for companies to rise productivity during an inflationary period, it's all important, What comes to my mind is this sophism that has emphasised the Keynesian multiplier can be used a monetary word in the favor of a more productive tissue, it is important to intuitively write

$$p_t = g(m_t) + I_t + \epsilon_t$$

Where g is an increasing function and I is the investments up to time t .

What this states is the fact consumption adds up to productivity intuitively in a time

of low production, it's very important to understand how the Keynesian multiplier is willing to change productivity upward if investments are rationally used on the company productive labour force.

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